

History Articles of Interest to Archaeologists. Annotated Bibliography

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Archaeology and history overlap. In fact, the first archaeological records in Chenango County were written by historians because no archaeologists were present. The first archaeologists did not appear locally until 1950, when the Chenango Chapter of the New York State Archaeological Association was founded. This gap of a century and a half allowed plenty of time for destruction to occur. Burial mounds were destroyed by 1810. I suspect that several Euro-American cemeteries were established atop Indian burial mounds and am currently researching this topic.

Here is an annotated bibliography of some local history articles that could be of interest to local archaeologists. It is listed alphabetically by authors and chronologically for each author.

Citations prefixed with a * are available only online. To request copies: windsorda@roadrunner.com .

Clark, Hiram C. *History of Chenango County, containing the Divisions of the County and Sketches of the Towns; Indian Tribes and Titles; Gov. Clinton's Purchase of the County Townships, Early Inhabitants and Settlements; Also: Land Patents; Rise and Progress of Agriculture, Manufactures and Trade; Annals of the Chenango Canal; Church History; Eminent Men and Statesmen, Professions, Etc. Etc.* Norwich, NY: Thompson & Pratt. 1850. 120 pages.

[This is the basic history book for Chenango County and is the primary document for many subsequent publications. Indian history is on pages 5-23.]

Cochrane, Mildred English. *From Raft to Railroad. A History of the Town of Greene Chenango County, New York 1792-1867.* Ithaca, NY: Cayuga Press. 1967. Reprinted by Binghamton, NY: Johnson City Publishing Company. 1991. Volume 1: 392 pages.

[Volume 1: page 9 first settler. 50-56 Indians.]

Cochrane, Folsom, Mildred English. *Echoes of the Past or Annals of the Town of Greene Chenango County, New York 1867-1967.* [Original publisher not given] 1971. Reprinted by Binghamton, NY: Johnson City Publishing Company. 1991. Volume 2: 386 pages.

[Volume 2: pages 351-386 Cemeteries. Some cemeteries were built upon Indian burial grounds.]

Chenango County History Essays 2023 February 19: 1-4

Galpin, Henry J. *Annals of Oxford, New York, 1906*. Oxford, NY: Self published. 1906. 568 pages.
[Indian antiquities 51-53 ; Indian stories 262-267 ; Visited by Indians 384-385.]

Hedrick, Ulysses Prentiss. Indian agriculture. Chapter II pages 20-39 in: *A History of Agriculture in the State of New York*. New York, NY: Hill and Wang. 1933. First American Century Edition 1966. 466 pages.

Mather, J.H. ; Brockett, L.P. Chenango County [Antiquities, Mounds]. In: *A Geographical History of the State of New York: Embracing Its History, Government, Physical Features, Climate, Geology, Mineralogy, Botany, Zoology, Education, Internal Improvements, &c with a separate map of Each County*. Utica, NY: H.H. Hawley. 1848. Pages 269-272.

McElligott, Corey C. ; McElligott, Darren C. ; McElligott, Patrick R. *Water Man. A Native People's History of the North East*. [Guilford, NY]: Waterfalls Press. 2011. [Unpaged. 354 pages.]
[This book is a goldmine of archaeological finds that the authors made in the Guilford area and may not have been published before. The book has no index or page numbers, so finding anything is awkward.]

Merian, A. Gail. *New York Susquehanna & Western Railroad Mile Markers*. Norwich, NY: Self published. 2011. 27 pages.

Merian, A. Gail. Documenting the Indian Castle. *Journal of the Chenango County Historical Society* 2017 Summer; 6:35- 45. [The author ties together the complex literature on this Norwich site.]

Merian, A. Gail. Thick Neck: documenting a legend. *Journal of the Chenango County Historical Society* 2017 Summer; 6:58-73. [The author straightens out all the different stories about this famous character.]

Merian, A. Gail ; Moyer, David. A portable petroglyph from the Ralph Zorda collection of Native American artifacts. *Journal of the Chenango County Historical Society* 2022 Summer; 10: 43-49. [Silver Lake, Pittsfield, Otsego County]

Parker, AC. The Archaeological History of New York (Part 2). Albany, NY: *New York State Museum Bulletin* 1920 September-October; (237,238): 471-473.
[While much of the information in here may be outdated, this book was once a classic.]

Smith, James H. *History of Chenango and Madison Counties, New York with Illustrations and Biographical Sketches of Some of Its Prominent Men and Pioneers*. Syracuse, NY: D. Mason & Co. 1880. 789 pages. [The first 70 pages are on the aborigines.]

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Smith, Richard. The Susquehanna: by wagon road from Canajoharie to Otsego Lake; thence by canoe to old Oghwaga, 106 miles; May 13 - June 5, 1769. In: *A Tour of the Hudson, the Mohawk, the Susquehanna, and the Delaware in 1769. Edited, with a Short History Of Pioneer Settlements by Francis W. Halsey.* 1769. Reprinted by Purple Mountain Press, Fleischmanns, NY. 1989. pages 95-135. [Edition by Ira J. Friedman, Port Washington, NY, 1964 has this on pages 63-64.]

[The earliest written record about Indians in Chenango County.]

Tiffany, Nelson B. Indians at King Settlement. In: Sesquicentennial Book Committee (Evans, Patricia ; Tiffany, Nelson B. ; Hazard, Mildred E. ; Decker, Janet ; Chirlin, Sally ; Whaley, June ; Steward, Sharon) *Next Stop Galena! A Historical Perspective of North Norwich, New York 1849-1999.* North Norwich, NY: 1999. 282 pages.

[Page 55: An Indian trail went along Thompson Creek. Artifacts were found near the Buell dam. I suspect that this dam was east of Mudge King Road.]

Windsor, Donald A. Stone Piles in Chenango County. *Archives of the SciAesthetics Institute* 2000 December; 1(2): 33-50. [The basic publication on stone cairns with all of the explanations known at the time.]

Windsor, Donald A. ; Storms, Dale C. Indian mound in Norwich. *Chenango County Historian's Journal* 2001 July-December; 2(3-4): 13, 20.

Windsor, Donald A. ; Storms, Dale C. What did Chenango County look like? Part 1. The historical record. *Chenango County Historian's Journal* 2002 July-September; 3(3): 1-9.

Windsor, Donald A. ; Storms, Dale C. What did Chenango County look like? Part 2. Hatch, potatoes, bounties, predators, pigeons, pines. *Chenango County Historian's Journal* 2002 October - December; 3(4): 1-6.

Windsor, Donald A. Indian mounds. *Souvenirs of Yesteryear. Exploring Chenango County, New York.* 2010; 3: 17-19. [Photo of a mound in Brookfield, with some local archaeologists.]

Windsor, Donald A. The Tarbell Farms: Documenting the Story. *Journal of the Chenango County Historical Society* 2013 Summer; 2: 65-69. [The Tarbell foundations are among the best ruins in Chenango County, but the stories about them are confusing and contradictory. The documented truth is presented here.]

Windsor, Donald A. Ganasowada to Canasawacta. *Journal of the Chenango County Historical Society* 2018 Summer; 7: 107-112. [Ganasowada is the Native American name for the Canasawacta Creek, the Mount Hope mound, the Indian Castle, and the Jamba Flats.]

Windsor, Donald A. First Europeans were in Chenango County in 1615. *Journal of the Chenango County Historical Society* 2021 Summer; 9: 42-50.

*Windsor, Donald A. Stone Cairn Clusters As Marketplaces. *Chenango County History Essays 2022* May 24: 1-4. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27315.09766 [The title is offered as a hypothesis.]

Chenango County History Essays 2023 February 19: 1-4

*Windsor, Donald A. Cairn Sites Aligned with Archaeological Sites. *Chenango County History Essays 2022 May 29: 1-6.* DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34025.98401
[The White Site is aligned with Fort Stanwix and with some stone cairn sites.]

*Windsor, Donald A. Prehistory of Chenango County. *Chenango County History Essays 2022 June 18: 1-14.* DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16301.77281 [The author presents his overview of 10,000 years in 14 pages.]

Windsor, Donald A. The earliest settlers in Chenango County. *Journal of the Chenango County Historical Society 2022 Summer; 10: 1-5,123-124.*
[The earliest documented Euro-American settlers in each town are listed.]

Windsor, Donald A. Coal in Chenango County. *Journal of the Chenango County Historical Society 2022 Summer; 10: 99-103, 138-139.* [Coal was an important factor in why and how Chenango County developed.]

*Windsor, Donald A. Chenango River as a Lake. *Chenango County History Essays 2022 July 4: 1-4.* DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13495.19365 [Archaeological sites often occur where smaller streams flow into larger ones. Higher water levels in the River would mean that sites should be looked for farther from today's shoreline.]

*Windsor, Donald A. Prehistory of the City of Norwich. *Chenango County History Essays 2022 August 8: 1-6.* DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35986.32965

*Windsor, Donald A. Prehistory of the Unadilla River Valley. *Chenango County History Essays 2022 August 29: 1-7.* DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13982.61763

*Windsor, Donald A. Prehistory of the Chenango River Valley through Greene. *Chenango County History Essays 2022 December 6: 1-9.* DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32869.88804

*Windsor, Donald A. Prehistory of the Chenango River Valley through Oxford. *Chenango History Essays 2023 January 13: 1-8.* DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32869.88804

*Windsor, Donald A. Prehistory of the Chenango River Valley through Sherburne. *Chenango History Essays 2023 February 8: 1-6.*

*Windsor, Donald A. Prehistory of the Chenango River Valley through North Norwich. *Chenango History Essays 2023* In preparation.